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THESIS BOOK

**THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN PROJECT PERFORMANCE
IN MOGADISHU SOMALIA: A CASE STUDY OF GREDO,
MOGADISHU, SOMALIA**

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MASTER PROGRAM: PROJECT MANAGEMENT

**THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS OF
THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE OR ARTS IN**

MARCH 2021

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this project book is my own work under the supervision of me and that it has not been submitted to for any other university,

Institution, or college.

Name: _____

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Date:...../...../.....

APPROVAL

I certify this research report satisfies the partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of Master degree at Accord university

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Faculty of project management at accord University.

Academic year: 2020-2021

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Date: ____/____/2021

DEDICATION

This study is especially dedicated to my beloved mother Faduma Abdi Ahmed who give me the greatest love, mercy, supporting, encouragement, nourishment, happiness, protection from harmful things to me, teaching and all great appreciation to me. I thank my dear Friends and Family without their motivation, knowledge, guidance and love I wouldn't have the goals I have to strive and be best to reach my dreams.

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Honor be to Allah who made it possible to write this paper and gave me talent and ability to Complete my proposal book, secondly, I wish to express my supervisor Prof Issa Kabudula And the research committee for their patience, advice, and smart material they have given to This work and the errors they have saved to my proposal which without their contribution I Wouldn't have avoided making.

I also wish to thank all my lecture teachers of Accord University particularly

Dean of the Faculty: _____

Prof: _____ dean _____

And the rest of my lectures who all deserve to be congratulating for the success of the University and I also thanks my dear friends specially my classmates

ABSTRACT

Background

Globally, in the late 1970s and early 1980s managers and scholars became interested in the topic of “communication on project performance. Communication has been long recognized as a significant factor in organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and innovation and as a foundation for organization’s management system and practices (Perrow, 2010).

Objective: The general objective of this study is to examine the role of communication in project performance in Mogadishu Somalia.

Methodology: the study will follow a descriptive research design, whereby qualitative and quantitative approaches will be used to gain insight to variables; this is because the researcher intends to find out the relationship between variables. The correlational design was used to determine the significant relationship between the community participation and health service delivery (Creswell, 2009). The study will also use survey design, this will be used to collect data from a large sample of respondents. In addition, descriptive correlational design will be used to determine significant relationship between variables. This study will also follow a descriptive research design, whereby qualitative and quantitative research approaches will be used to gain insight to variables it will be descriptive in that it will describe the characteristics of respondents.

Result: Most of respondents of this study 30(41.1%) were between 18-27 years and 28-47 years, while 4(5.9%) were 48-57 years and 58 and above the researcher indicates the most of respondents were 18-27 years and 28-47 years old. Most of respondents of this study 50 (73.5 %) were single and 18(26.5%) were married. The researcher indicates the most of respondents were single. So, the most of respondents were singles. Most of respondents of this study 20(29.4%) were Primary, secondary and Tertiary level, while only 8(11.8%) had no formal education level, so this result indicates that the most of respondents were Primary, secondary and Tertiary level. So the most of respondents are Primary, secondary and Tertiary. Most of respondents of this study 34(50%) were employed, and 34(50%) were unemployed. So the researcher indicates that the most of respondents were employed and unemployed. 38 respondents with the percentage of (55.9%) agreed that You feel that your opinions are considered in the team, 12 respondents with the percentage of (17.6%) strongly agreed it, 7 respondents with the percentage of (10.3%) were neutral.

On the other hand, 7 other respondents with the percentage of (10.3%) strongly disagreed it, while only 4 respondents with the percentage of (5.9%) disagreed it.

Conclusion: Successfully managing a project from start to finish requires certain key skills. Scheduling, time management, and the ability to negotiate with internal and external parties are all critical competencies. Leadership, risk management, and critical thinking similarly all fall high on the list.

But the skill that is perhaps most important to project management is the one that underlies all of these others: Communication.

Without strong communication skills, project managers would find it incredibly difficult, if not impossible, to effectively manage their teams and coordinate efforts in order to bring about a project's successful resolution.

Recommendation: In this section the researcher suggested some recommendations:

1. Although the study was carried out in Mogadishu, there is a need for further research across the whole country.
2. Other researchers should examine the ties between the study results and the reality that exists in the study area.
3. Other researchers are encouraged to test the generalizability of this study by conducting the same study in other districts within Mogadishu or other regions of Somalia.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This study will be carried out in order to examine the role of communication in project performance of GREDO (Gargaar Relief and Development Organization) projects in Mogadishu Somalia. GREDO (Gargaar Relief and Development Organization) is an indigenous local NGO. Non-profit non-partisan, non-political and voluntary organization based in Baidoa-Mogadishu. To reach the most affected grass-root communities in Bay and Bakool regions in Mogadishu effectively and efficiently, the necessity of local partnership in relief program appeared. This chapter introduces the background of the study, statement of the problem, and purpose of the study, objectives of the study, research questions, scope of the study, and significance of the study.

1.1 Background of the Study

This section encompasses four perspectives namely historical, theoretical, conceptual and contextual perspectives.

1.1.1 Historical Perspective

Globally, in the late 1970s and early 1980s managers and scholars became interested in the topic of “communication on project performance. Communication has been long recognized as a significant factor in organizational efficiency, effectiveness, and innovation and as a foundation for organization’s management system and practices (Perrow, 2010). This is because communication through history has been used to determine how decisions are made and how employees’ response to the environment hence influencing the performance of projects.

Project performance has been acknowledged for thousands of years since the Egyptian era, however, it has been about half a century ago that organizations started applying systematic project management tools and techniques to complex projects (Carayannis, 2003). It should be noted that, project performance has become an important issue in this globalized world. Globally, project performance predispositions are shaped by a host of factors. Empirical studies have revealed that there are numerous determinants of project performance (Flamholtz& Randle, 2011).

In Africa, project management has long been practiced by many countries such as Africa, Nigeria . The South African Chapter was established in 1982 but was replaced in 1992 by Project Management South Africa. In 2000 the Council for the Built Environment was promulgated by an act of parliament and this brought into existence the South African Council for Construction and Project Managers, a statutory body that any professional who intends acting as project manager, needs to register, also several voluntary organizations in South Africa which represent the interests of the various project management disciplines (Eaton & Kilby, 2015).

Project Managers found themselves in the position, where they were unprepared and manage projects that happened to cross their desks. Despite the fact that Project Management is now a recognized “profession” many of the appointed Project Managers are not dedicated Project Managers, but were rather appointed to protect some or other interest and are often unprepared for the challenges of continually shaping internal and external context, and frequently lacking the creativity, awareness and sensitivity such a role demands (Robert and Pantaleo, 1999).

In Somalia, several organizations team up with the government to deliver humanitarian services. For example, humanitarian Aid from the European Commission focused on nutrition, water and sanitation, livestock, food security, shelter and assistance to internally displaced populations and assistance to Somali refugees in Kenya. Additionally, since 2006 the European Commission has allocated €13 million to assist Somali refugees in Kenya (Somalia, fact sheet; EU, 2009). Projects in the past have focused mainly on three sectors: i) Governance and security, including support to institutional building, reconciliation, rule of law, human rights and capacity building for Somali Non State Actors; ii) Social sectors, including support to primary and secondary education, adult literacy, teacher and vocational training, health systems strengthening and maternal health care and improved access to safe water in urban and rural areas; iii) Agriculture, livestock, food security and early warning (Jofreh & Masoumi, 2013).

Despite the monies that have been poured in Somalia over the years, the lives of the inhabitants seem not to change fundamentally. Many local for profit organizations existing in the country, especially the capital city Mogadishu, are ran by unqualified people who do not have the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities to succeed in projects. Although, there is a growing number of studies as those cited above project management, appropriate little about managerial competencies and project performance in Mogadishu, Somalia. In fact, less research supports the link between those factors mentioned earlier, hence a gap, which this study sought to fill (Cian & Cervai, 2014).

1.1.2 Contextual perspective

Gargaar Relief and Development Organization is one of the largest, leading Somalia non-government organizations (NGO) working in the areas of development and policy advocacy. Its major areas of interventions/ engagements include, but not limited to, rural development, human rights and social justice. The organization has implemented during these period different projects including relief and emergency programs and later improved into rehabilitation and developmental programs. GREDO is dedicated to promoting the rights and status of marginalized groups enabling them to seek and secure sustainable livelihoods to create a society that has equitable access to all opportunities. The organization maintains excellent relations with international and civil society organizations within the country in the various aspects of relief, rehabilitation, development, peace building and human rights.

The objectives of GREDO are to: facilitate and participate in the humanitarian efforts of the international community in all their efforts to reach vulnerable groups in the operational areas of the organizational through partnership, the kind of changes required to alleviate poverty in the long-term and to address its root causes, provide primary health care targeting men and women, and basic secondary health services with focus on sexual reproductive and child health through nutrition program and health services; for under five children, pregnant and lactating mothers, measures, which increase food production or income-generation and employment opportunities, promote the capacities of the small-scale business, farmers and livestock herders by providing them with tailor-made training courses, expertise and financial assistance, address the economic and social problems facing poor people through three interrelated principles: participation, equity and sustainability, mobilize grass-root communities in order to enhance their awareness on democracy, peace, human rights protection and their potentials as individuals and groups, investigate, document, monitor and advocate for cases on human rights violation with particular consideration to the domestic violence caused by the civil war, implement short-term and long-term educational strategies and programs to fight against illiteracy.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Researchers and professionals in different fields have recognized the role of communication in the performance of organizations (e.g., Ankrah, 2007; Deal and Kennedy, 1982; Peters and Waterman, 1982; Kotter and Heskett, 1992). The performance of each project is evaluated by the level at which it attains its goals and objectives and for every project to be successfully performed, it needs effective organizational performance.

In GREDO, Construction Projects such as: Schools, Roads and water drainage faced delay in its performance due to poor organizational culture. For instance, in communication, the project team failed to make effective communication which significantly hampered the progress of the project. It is believed that lack of management style among some workers and ineffective organizational culture caused the project to delay its performance. (GREDO,HRM REPORT, 2017).

As a result, the project almost came to a standstill due to lack of effective communication. The result of these failed projects, a monumental economic loss is incurred in terms of heavy costs, periodic waste of resources, Wastage of resources overtime, and projects that metamorphose into bottomless pits gulping scarce resources with no concrete completion time in sight (Miguel, 2015). On the other hand, poor communication such as lack of internal communication, poor leadership style and lack of discussion and low of organizational values and norms caused poor project performance. There have been many GREDO projects such as borehole projects, building schools and also roads. These projects are aimed at empowering primary stakeholders in GREDO projects. Some have been successfully implemented and completed while others have only been implemented but not completed (World Bank, 2017). Some employees perform at slow rate since they find it not easy to react to external/internal changes as systems are designed for stability, too many structural layers at GREDO slow down and reduce communication effectiveness among workers. The authority at GREDO is maintained centrally, reducing the effectiveness of front-line staff. This study therefore seeks to assess the role of communication on the performance of GREDO projects in Mogadishu Somalia.

This study therefore seeks to assess the role of communication on the organizational performance of GREDO projects in Mogadishu Somalia.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

I. IGAREDO as an organization may be able to improve the performance of its projects as the study may provide an understanding of the current strengths and weaknesses in their organization culture.

II. The study findings may assist project managers by contributing knowledge and experiences regarding the role of communication in improving performance and productivity in the organization. Effective communication is an important factor in advancing performance. Once organizations achieve effective communication, they might continue to diversify project without affecting performance. Project managers may benefit from the results of the study by obtaining relevant information in the area of communication. Project managers may use the information to improve performance and productivity in the organization.

III. To the academia, the study may provide new knowledge and can be a point of reference and may also open avenues for further research and for the researcher, it will give more in-depth knowledge in research and means to write a research paper on organization culture and project performance.

1.4 PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The general objective of this study is to examine the role of communication in project performance in Mogadishu Somalia.

1.4.1 Specific objective

- 1.** To assess the role of verbal communication on organizational performance in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- 2.** To examine the role of verbal communication on construction projects in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- 3.** To establish the role of writing communication on construction projects in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTION

1. What is the role of verbal communication on organizational performance of Gredo in Mogadishu, Somalia?
2. What is the role of verbal communication on construction projects of Gredo in Mogadishu, Somalia Mogadishu, Somalia?
3. What is to establish the role of writing communication on construction projects of Gredo in Mogadishu, Somalia?

1.6 Theoretical perspective

The study will be based on organizational performance theory by Allaire & Firsirotu (1984). The theory states that effective organizational culture includes successful strategy, effective leadership, excellent employee performance and ethical philosophy (Denison, 1990). In an effective organizational performance, members of the organization understand how to interact with various stakeholders (Schein, 1985). Each organization has a different organizational performance that covers a wide range of behaviors in the organization (Schein, 1985). Project managers use an effective organizational culture theory to execute an organizational strategy and to improve performance in the organization (Monzavia, Mirabib, & Jamshidic, 2013).

Organizational performance theory includes four essential elements: adaptability, mission, consistency and involvement (Childress, 2013). The reason behind organizational culture theory is the project managers' perception that an organizational culture is an essential factor to influence the organization's effectiveness. Project managers use organizational culture theory to address different project issues in the organization (Schneider, Ehrhart, & Macey, 2013).

Organizational performance theory involves beliefs, assumptions, and symbols of organizational members that define the process in which a company conducts its project (Schneider et al., 2013). Project managers use an effective organizational culture to influence performance and productivity (Shahzad, Luqman, Khan, & Shabbir, 2012). Organizational performance has the potential to influence the organization environment, work habits, performance, productivity, and profitability (Linnenluecke & Griffiths, 2010).

Organizational performance is the shared basic assumptions, values, and beliefs of the members of the organization (Martínez-Cañas & Ruiz-Palomino, 2014). Organizational performance is the way that managers and employees solve problems in the organization (Schneider et al., 2013).

1.7. Conceptual perspective

Organizational performance is a set of values, beliefs, and behavior patterns that differentiate one organization from other organizations (Ortega-Parra & Sastre-Castillo, 2013). King (2012) defined organizational performance as a system of values that subconsciously and silently drives people to make each choice and decision in the organization. Project managers use organizational performance and corporate performance interchangeably because both terms refer to the same underlying phenomenon (Childress, 2013).

Andish (2013) defined project performance as balancing the competing demands for project quality, scope, time, and cost, as well as meeting the varying concerns and expectations of the project stakeholders. A project is considered successful if it was completed within its budget estimate, within its initial scheduled time frame, and performed as it was designed to function (Sylvester & Abdul Rani, 2011). Project performance is a strategic management concept where project efforts must be aligned with both short and long-term goals of the company (Harun, 2011).

1.8 Scope of the study

Geographically, the study will be carried out from GAREDO in Mogadishu Somalia. GREDO is an indigenous local NGO. Non-profit non-partial, non-political and voluntary organization based in Mogadishu. To reach the most affected grass-root communities in Mogadishu region effectively and efficiently, the necessity of local partnership in relief program appeared. Responding to the partnership need, a group of Somali intellectuals and well-wishers initiated in December 1992 a local non-governmental organization called Gargaar Relief and Development Organization (GREDO). The organization has implemented during these period different projects including relief and emergency programs and later improved into rehabilitation and developmental programs. GREDO is dedicated to promoting the rights and status of marginalized groups enabling them to seek and secure sustainable livelihoods to create a society that has equitable access to all opportunities. The organization maintains excellent relations with international and civil society organizations within the country in the various aspects of relief, rehabilitation, development, peace building and human rights.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter contains theoretical review, conceptual framework and related studies categorized on the objectives of the study, empirical studies and the research gap.

2.1 Theoretical review

Communication theory

The study will be guided by the communication theory developed by Allaire and Firsirotu(1984). The theory identified four elements of communication which included involvement, consistency, adaptability and mission. The four communication theory elements are essential in developing and maintaining an effective communication in the organization (Kotrba et al., 2012). The involvement and consistency as internal factors in developing an effective organizational culture. Adaptability and mission are external factors in maintaining an effective organizational culture.

Müller &Turner, (2010, p. 24) highlight that communications play an important role for the success of any projects. In any successful project where project management appeared to be done, the capabilities of communication are the main factor for the project success. In addition, 3

Communication is very important in the case of medium complexity, maintenance project and innovation process. The authors further explained communication as „lively communicator addresses others and win support“ then the communication inspire staff and audience and accessibility (Müller & Turner, 2010, p. 24). In addition, it has argued that communication is a key competence for project leaders in much focused in information system and organizational change projects (Müller & Turner, 2010, p. 25). It is the only way through communication that the project officers build relationship with the stakeholders. Communication might not only be the interaction forwarded by the project manager, it sometimes is the sponsor involvement in to the board or other senior stake holders (Müller & Turner, 2010, p. 72).

Hassanpour (2015) noted that involvement as a critical factor for communication effectiveness. Involvement includes transparent communication, employee-focused leadership, and strong interpersonal relationships in the organization (Engelen et al., 2014).

In an effective organizational culture, project managers encourage high employee involvement and participation of members of the organization in major organizational activities (O'Reilly et al., 2014). When employees participate in the organizational decision-making process, they develop a sense of ownership, trust, and loyalty for the organization (Denison, 1990). A sense of ownership and responsibility are part of the effective communication elements. Sense of ownership, trust, and loyalty are important factors to motivating employees in the organization (Kotrba et al., 2012).

When employees participate in the organizational decision-making process, they become more responsible and accountable for their actions (Denison, 1990). However, Givens (2012) argued that a high level of involvement in various activities creates a lack of specialization, where difficulty exists to identify the responsible person for the particular assignment. In an effective organizational culture, members of the organization from different backgrounds fairly share the organization's values, beliefs, and symbols in the organization (Mousavi, et al., 2015).

Effective communication exists when a group of people comes together from a different background to reach a common purpose. When members share the organization's values and beliefs, they understand and coordinate their responsibility consistent with organizational values. Schein (2010) indicated that when organization members share values and beliefs in the organization, they could maintain effective communication and strong communication (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). In an effective organizational culture, project managers establish an effective communication, which is important to coordinate employees' activity and increase involvement in the organizational decision-making process (Givens, 2012). Communication emerges from the collection of organizational members' behaviors. Effective communication never exists without a group of people, shared assumptions, and effective communication (Schein, 2010; Sok, Blommel, & Tromp, 2014).

Communication network are characterized by a number of interrelated components, including the amount and direction of communication, degree of centralization and the distribution of communication nodes and clusters (Tushman and Katz., 1980, p. 1071). The authors also discussed that social communication system contribute important role in the process of information from external environment in order to achieve better decision making process (Tushman and Katz, 1980, p. 1072). Project communication is the measure of absolute amount of technical communication in a project per person.

The common six exclusive communication measures in any projects are: communication within the project, communication to other areas within a project department, communication to other area outside the department, communication to areas in to larger organization, communication to external operational areas and communication to external professional outside the parent organization (Tushman & Katz, 1980, p. 1076).

Knowledge sharing is the outcome of formal and informal communication. The formal can be by formal technology fairs, scheduled meetings or request of information. Whereas the informal mechanism can be bench marking research and product or service demonstration (Lawson et al., 2009, p. 156).

In an effective organizational culture, project managers define the organization mission by providing purpose and meaning to every major part of the organization's mission (Givens, 2012). The mission contains clear direction and vision, strategic decision and intent and goals and objectives of the organization that members use to guide the activities of the organization (Mousavi et al., 2015). In an effective organizational culture, project managers use the organization's mission and vision to determining the organization short and long-term goals (Nongo& Ikyanyon1, 2012). Project managers use the organization mission to provide appropriate direction to internal and external stakeholders (Raza et al., 2014).

Review of Related literature

The review of related literature is presented following the study objectives;

2.3 .1 Effect of values and norms on project performance

Values are the core of the culture and can be expressed as the beliefs and ideals to choose between two options such as; good and evil. In addition, values are the standards that guide project performance conducts in different situations. Effective values or norms of organizations develop a clear and comprehensive project performance so that everyone is aware of and can be contribute. Organization values as the following: integrity and honesty (maintaining the highest levels of integrity and honesty at all times, and will preserve human rights), justice (providing fair and tactful services to all segments of society), recognizing achievements (appreciating and evaluating achievements made by individuals and by the community, by encouraging team spirit and motivating initiatives at all levels), effective communication (believing that effective

communication with the public and private sectors is of vital importance to accomplish our coveted goals and project performance), excellence (making sure to pursue excellence in all our work and ensure that our activities are assessed effectively and efficiently to meet that the project been performed well) (Eaton & Kilby, 2015).

Schein (2010) noted that management with weak communication lacks transparent and consistent communication in the organization. In a weak organizational culture, employees behave in a manner inconsistent with the organization priorities because of insufficient communication and lack of uniform direction from the leadership (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). When the communication is weak, the organization existence is at risk because organization members have different values and beliefs, where they may work against the management's priority.

Loyal and engaged employees are important to maintain an effective communication and to improve performance in the organization. For example, Pinho et al. (2014) noted that employees with a sense of ownership might significantly improve performance and productivity in the organization. When employees have a sense of ownership and responsibility, they may fulfill their responsibility without close supervision and control (Denison, 1990). Project managers can use their time to concentrate on other priorities in the organization.

2.3.2 Effect of organization management on project performance

Denison (1990) explained the impacts of communication on project performance. A quantitative study results indicate a positive relationship between communication and project performance (Jofreh & Masoumi, 2013). A case study research results also show a strong culture as a driving factor for organizational performance (Pinho, Rodrigues, & Dibb, 2014).

According to Bourne and Walker (2004) in most organizations, project managers are accountable for the successful delivery of complete projects. Increasingly, this success depends on project managers' processing and utilizing skills and competencies that may initially appear contradictory. A successful project manager must demonstrate flexibility and competency in many area, hard and soft skills, introverted and reflective, extroverted and social behavior. Many of the initiatives for improving the practice and profession of project management have been focused on enhancing techniques and method associated with skills that included effective management of time, cost and scope (Hartnell et al., 2011).

Communication is a motivational instrument in promoting performance in the organization (Jofreh&Masoumi, 2013). The coordinated effort of managers and employees may contribute to a positive working environment (Miguel, 2015). Schein (2010) noted that employees might motivate and improve their performance when they work in a positive working environment. The study findings showed that loyal and engaged employees promote effective communication to improve performance and productivity in the organization (Fiordelisi& Ricci, 2014).

Project management is rapidly growing focus discipline within many organizations and business ventures, however searching an optimal way of operating and continuous management of projects are one of the big challenges (Tonnquist, 2008, p. 1). Projects have been a big concern in any organization whether it is private or public firm. One of the indications can be “everyone in their professional life comes across different projects directly or indirectly”, the study also indicates that projects are temporary organizations and mandated to the project manager to lead the project until it is closed when the project actually expires. (Tonnquist, 2008, p. 6). Müller, (2009, p. 15) discusses the idea that, the heart of each project task is to create an outcome, the outcomes have to be accomplished by people, different costs, certain boundaries of time and related constraints. Therefore, projects can be considered as the organization of different resources including people for the accomplishment of specific outcomes with an indicated start & end date, however projects reside in the organization permanently. A similar study made by (Blackstone et al., 2009, p. 7029) defines project management as “an endeavor with the specific objective and limited time”.

Several experts, researchers, professional organizations and different international standards have defined projects in their own perspectives. (Katalin et al., 2011, p. 253) defines project management as the art of achieving the illusion that any outcome is the result of a predetermined series of acts. Graham (1985, cited in Katalin et al., 2011, p. 253) mentioned that projects are always a set of different activities performed by a set of people. Graham (1985) also stresses that projects are fixed budget and fixed time. Based on the German Society for Project Management (GPM), projects are a venture characterized by special conditions like human constraints. It has been believed that project management has begun with the beginning of the Manhattan project, which developed the first atomic bomb late in the 1940s, since then the project management techniques developed step by step (Sylvain & Christoph, 2010, p. 1).

Strong communication includes an important role in aligning the organization's current and future direction (Raza et al., 2014). In contrast, management with weak or ineffective communication has the potential to affect profitability and productivity. In a weak organizational culture, employees have a problem to define the organization's values and to determine the right process of conducting project in the organization (Childress, 2013). The project management skill competence is the ability to perform Project Management activities to the levels of performance expected. The demonstrable performance of the individual in executing Project Management tasks and provides the technical skills for project performance in terms of scope, time, cost and quality. With regards to project management, this managerial skill is used in the conveying of project information to others and must be done so with efficiency given the highly technical, detailed nature of the work. Studies suggest that project leaders deal with complex ideas and vast amounts of information. In addition, they must engage in constant coordination among multiple organizations and stakeholders, and all while working within the restrictions created by the conflicting relationship of complete project responsibility and little formal authority (Shahzad et al., 2012).

2.3.3 Effect of organization structure on project performance

In a strong organizational culture, project managers may develop and maintain a strong cultural foundation in the organization (Simoneaux & Stroud, 2014). The foundation work includes establishing the organization members' working culture and developing a set of rules and trends of doing project in the organization (Flamholtz & Randle, 2011). Customers and other stakeholders use the organization members' culture and their work trends to identify their organization from other organizations culture (Cian & Cervai, 2014). Customers and other stakeholders may perceive and use the communication as a distinguishing factor in identifying a good organization from a bad organization (Childress, 2013). A project manager's leadership style, communication, collaboration and the cohesiveness of a project team (Yang et al., 2011) are related to project success, especially in the case of high complexity projects in the areas of manufacturing, building, industry and infrastructure.

Project managers use a strong communication to substitute formal rules and regulations in the organization (Denison, 1990). Schein (2010) noted that establishing a set of standards and trends in the organization mainly includes creating a well-defined communication channel among employees and managers. Project managers may use the communication channel to develop transparent communication and to encourage a culture of sharing and teamwork among members of the organization. Management of projects requires knowledge of modern management as well as an understanding of the design and construction process of projects (Al-Tmeemy, Abdul-Rahman, & Harun, 2011). Specifically, project management encompasses a set of objectives which may be accomplished by implementing a series of operations subject to resources constraints (Cao, Huo, Li, & Zhao, 2015).

In a strong organizational culture, employees and project managers have an excellent professional quality that contributes to performance improvement in the organization (Pinho et al., 2014). Professional quality contains (a) respect and dignity between employees and managers, (b) high commitment to customer services, and (c) motivation and moral engagement to achieve organizational priorities (Busse, 2014). When employees and project managers develop respect and dignity between them, they can help each other and may integrate their knowledge and experience to improve performance in the organization (Miguel, 2015).

Empirical studies

Fauziah (2011) noted that performance of the company can be described by imperceptible organizational basics (Detert, 2000). Wilderom and Van den Berg (2000), stated that there are five elements in describing the intangible basics of organizational cultures which are empowerment, internal and external orientations, improvement orientation, and human resource orientation that support the dependencies of company performance on the culture of organization. At the same time, the practices in the company that raise a proactive market orientation, strong challenger orientation and expert information management have been argued by Glunk and Wilderom(1999), hence the workers who achieving the competitive advantage will be given a reward.

According to Fey and Denison (2010), the measurements of finance will help the investigators to build threshold and benchmarking analyses.

The dependencies of Nigerian companies performance on the culture of organization has been examined by Ezirim (2010) and the results showed a significant positive correlation between them. According to Sadri and Lees (2001), the bad culture in the organization will give the bad performance as it can stop the company from adopting needed tactical or strategies changes. Besides that, Shore (2008) stated that the culture develops within the context of executive leadership and national cultures.

Belassi (2007) said that the communication represents the method of how the members think and act in order to establish the competence of the firm. Therefore, it can be summarized that the communication has more effect to the project performance compared to the national culture. In addition, Belassi (2007) also support the theory by doing several studies about the culture in organization the results shows that a proper communication creates good organizational performance.

Besides that, the argument about the relationship between the culture of organization and IT project performance also occurred. Akgun (2011) stated that a positive condition of work plays important role in ensuring the success of IT project. Comparative studies between US IT hires and Chinese that institutional socialism had a substantial impact on the IT hire insight and their ultimate performance when working on IT projects (King and Bu, 2005).

Furthermore, it is claimed that great performance of IT project comes from good leadership team (Thamhain, 2004). Therefore, there is a direct impact of communication towards IT project performance. Belassi (2007) developed a set of questionnaire based on the various definition of the culture in order to measure organizational culture. Cultural dimensions that Belassi, (2007) used in their research include management, positive work environment, leadership, and the orientation of results. The positive work atmospheres and leadership management are strongly related with each other (Belassi, 2007). Besides that, the results also propose that companies which have good environmental condition will help to boost the performance of the project rather than less comfortable condition of workplace. (Kloosterman, (2013).

2.5 Summary

The organization culture theory did not indicate feasible strategies to boost project performance. As the foregoing review, values and norms as a factor that influences communication has not been extensively tackled. A number of studies such as that of Mazita Mokhtar (2011); AzizanHjAzit (2014), Wan Khairul Anuar (2010); Wan Abdul Manan (2013), have been done covering the subject of communication however, none of them has covered the aspect of project performance through organization management and organizational structure hence providing a content gap that this study will cover. The gaps in the literature review will be filled during field data collection, which will be guided by the purpose and the objectives of the current study. However, this study will investigate the role of communication and its impact on project performance and the results that will fish out from this study will fill the gap between my study and other studies that already done.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the research design, the research population, and the sample size, sampling procedures, research instruments, validity and reliability of instruments, data gathering procedures, data analysis, ethical considerations and limitations of the study.

3.1 Research design

The study will follow a descriptive research design, whereby qualitative and quantitative approaches will be used to gain insight to variables; this is because the researcher intends to find out the relationship between variables. The correlational design was used to determine the significant relationship between the community participation and health service delivery (Creswell, 2009). The study will also use survey design, this will be used to collect data from a large sample of respondents. In addition, descriptive correlational design will be used to determine significant relationship between variables. This study will also follow a descriptive research design, whereby qualitative and quantitative research approaches will be used to gain insight to variables it will be descriptive in that it will describe the characteristics of respondents

3.2 Research population

The researcher was used a population of 82 respondents. Study population refers to the cumulative elements of study from an environment in which information is gathered from. The study population was involved 5 top authorities of GREDO, 12 officials from HRM department, 20 officials from Finance& Accounts department, 12 officials from procurement department, 14 officials from sales and marketing department, 19 casual workers of GREDO. The researcher will use these respondents because they are believed to have information on the communication and project performance.

3.3 Sample size

The sample size of the study consists of 82 of target population and is determined through purposive and random sampling methods. This is so because the nature of data to be generated requires different techniques for better understanding of the research problem under investigation. Besides this the approach is also commonly known for achieving higher degree of validity and reliability as well as elimination of biases.

The Slovene's formula will be used to determine the minimum sample size.

$$n = 68 \text{ respondents}$$

n = sample size

N = the population size

e = level of significance, fixed at 0.05

Table 3.1 Sample size and target population

Category	Target population	Sample size	Sampling techniques
Top authorities of GREDO	5	4	Purposive sampling
Officials from HRM department	12	10	Purposive sampling
Officials from Accounts & Finance department	20	17	Random sampling
Officials from sales and marketing department	14	12	Random sampling
Officials from procurement department	12	10	Random sampling
Casual workers	19	15	Stratified sampling
Total	82	68	

Source: Human resource department of GreDO, 2018

3.4 Sampling procedure

Simple random sampling will be used to select the respondents. From which all respondents are represented in the study and all will have a chance of being selected to participate in this study as respondents.

Purposive sampling

The researcher will also use purposive sampling. A purposive sample is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study. The researcher will purposely select officials from HRM department and the top authorities of GREDO. This is because it reaches a targeted sample quickly and these respondents are believed to have vital information about communication and project performance.

Stratified sampling

The study will also involve stratified sampling. Stratified sampling is a type of sampling method in which the total population is divided into smaller groups or strata to complete the sampling process. The strata is formed based on some common characteristics in the population data. After dividing the population into strata, the researcher randomly selects the sample proportionally. This refers to a sampling technique where by respondents are categorized into groups according to what they share in common. Casual workers will be stratified sampled. *Stratified random sampling accurately reflects the population* being studied because researchers are stratifying the entire population before applying random sampling methods. In short, it ensures each subgroup within the population receives proper representation within the sample.

3.5 Research instrument

3.5.1 Questionnaire

A questionnaire will be the major method used for data collection. The questionnaires will be preferred for this study because it enables the researcher reach a larger number of respondents within a short time, thus can make it easier to collect relevant information (Amin, 2005). The first section in the questionnaire will be the face sheet, to collect data on profile of respondents. The second section in the questionnaire will be organisation culture.

The third section of the questionnaire will have questions on performance of GREDO projects. All the questions are Likert Scaled on four points ranging from 1= strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree, and 4 = strongly agree. The questionnaires contain close-ended questions to collect quantifiable data relevant for precise and effective correlation of research variables. They will also be preferred to save time, enable respondents to easily fill out the questionnaires and keep them on the subject and relatively objective.

3.5.2 Interview guide

The interview guide will be used to collect information about the study from respondents who will be some of the directors of the GreDO and beneficiaries. The respondents will be asked questions including opinions on the subject matter.

3.6 Validity and reliability of the instrument

3.6.1 Validity

Here the questionnaire will be given to three lecturers (experts) to judge the validity of questions according to the objectives. After the assessment of the questionnaire, the necessary adjustments will be made bearing in mind the objectives of the study. Then a content validity index (CVI) will be computed using the following formula:

CVI =

A minimum of 0.75 of CVI will be used to test validity of the research instrument

3.6.2 Reliability

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, the researcher will use the test-retest method. The questionnaire will be given to 10 people and after two weeks, the same questionnaire will be given to the same people and the Cronbach Alpha will be computed using SPSS. The minimum Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.70 will be used to declare an instrument reliable (>0.70). This is because according to Amin (2005) 0.7 is the minimum required to declare the instrument reliable

3.7 Data gathering procedure

Before the administration of the questionnaires

Before the administration of the questionnaires the researcher will take an introductory letter from the post graduate school, the researcher will have to first seek authorization from the proposed respondents to conduct research and review the questions to avoid errors and ensure that only qualified respondents are approached.

During the administration of the questionnaires

The respondents will be requested to sign and answer the questionnaires. The researcher will emphasize retrieval of the questionnaires within three days from the date of distribution. And lastly, all returned questionnaires will be checked if all are answered.

After the administration of the questionnaires

The data gathered will be collected, coded into the computer and statistically treated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

3.8 Data Analysis

The frequency and percentage distribution will be used to determine the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The mean and standard deviations will be applied for the extent of organization culture and performance of GREDO projects.

The researcher will use Pearson's linear correlation coefficient (PLCC) to analyze the relationship between organization culture and performance of GREDO projects.

And regression analyze will be used to determine the significant effect between the variables and this will help in analyzing data on study objectives.

The following mean ranges and descriptions will be used to interpret responses:

For organization culture

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfactory
2.51-3.25	Agree	Satisfactory
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Unsatisfactory
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very unsatisfactory

For performance of GREDO projects

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very satisfactory
2.51-3.25	Agree	Satisfactory
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Unsatisfactory
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very unsatisfactory

3.9 Ethical considerations

To ensure confidentiality of the information provided by the respondents and to ascertain the practice of ethical in this study, the following activities will be implemented by the researcher:

1. Request the respondents to sign in the inform consent form
2. Acknowledge the authors quoted in this study and the author of standardized instrument through citations and referencing.
3. Present the findings in a generalized manner.

3.10 Limitations of the study

In view of the following threats to validity, the researcher allows 0.05 level of significance. Measures are also indicated in order to minimize if not to eradicate the threats to the validity of the findings of the study.

1. Extraneous variables which will be beyond the researcher's control such as respondent's honesty , personal biases and uncontrolled setting of the study .
2. Testing the use of research assistants can bring about inconsistency in the administration of the questionnaires in terms of time of administration, understanding of the items in the questionnaires and explanations given to the respondents. To minimize the threat, the research assistants will be oriented and briefed on the procedures to be done in data collection.

3. Attrition/Mortality: Not all questionnaires may be returned completely answered now even retrieved back due to circumstances on the part of the respondents such as travels, sickness, hospitalization and refusal/withdrawal to participate. In anticipation to this, the researcher will reserve more respondents by exceeding the minimum sample size. The respondents will also be reminded not to leave any item in the questionnaires unanswered and will be closely followed up as to the date of retrieval.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

This study will have focused the role of communication in project performance in Mogadishu Hodan District. The data has been analyzed by using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20 as data analyzing tool. This chapter presents the results of the analysis in tables that contains the type of responses. Its frequencies, and percentages were used to elaborate the percentage reactions for respondents in the study to the statements given in the questionnaire. This chapter highlights on data analysis, presentation and interpretation. The data analyzes and interpreted based on research questions as well as research objective.

4.1 Socio demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 4.1 Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	48	70.6	70.6	70.6
Valid Female	20	29.4	29.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4. 1, the majority of the respondents 48(70.6%) were male, while only 20(29.4%) were female. This indicates that most of those who participated the study were male.

Figure 4.1 Marital status

Table 4.2 Age of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-27 years	18	26.5	26.5	26.5
28-37 years	23	33.8	33.8	60.3
38-47 years	10	14.7	14.7	75.0
48-57 years	12	17.6	17.6	92.6
58 and above	5	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.2, the majority of the respondents 23(33.8%) were between 28 – 37 years, 18(26.5 %) were between 18 – 27 years, 23(33.8%) were either 38-47 years 10(14.7%) and 48 – 57 years, are 12(17.6%) while only 5(7.4%) were 58 and above years.

Figure 4.2 age of the respondents

Table 4.3 Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Single	25	36.8	36.8	36.8
Valid Married	43	63.2	63.2	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.3, the majority of the respondents 43(63.2%) were married, while 25(36.8%) were single. This indicates that more married respondents participated the study than single participants.

Figure 4.3 marital status

Table 4.4 Educational level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Secondary	4	5.9	5.9	5.9
Diploma	9	13.2	13.2	19.1
Bachelor	28	41.2	41.2	60.3
Master	22	32.4	32.4	92.6
Other	5	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.4, the majority of the respondents 28(41.2%) were bachelor degree, 22(32.4%) were master level, 9(13.2%) were diploma level, 4(5.9%) were secondary level, while 5(7.4%) had other levels of education.

Figure 4.4 educational level

Table 4.5 Occupation of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Employed	62	91.2	91.2	91.2
Valid Unemployed	6	8.8	8.8	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.5, the majority of the respondents 62(91.2%) were employed, while 6(8.8%) were unemployed.

Figure 4.5 occupation of the respondents

Table 4.6 You feel that your opinions are considered in the team

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	29	42.6	42.6	42.6
Agree	25	36.8	36.8	79.4
Neutral	8	11.8	11.8	91.2
Disagree	4	5.9	5.9	97.1
Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.6, the majority of the respondents 29(42.6%) strongly agreed that You feel that your opinions are considered in the team, 25(36.8%) agreed it, 8(11.8%) were neutral, 4(5.9%) disagreed it, while only 2(2.9%) strongly disagreed it. 4.

Figure 4.6 You feel that your opinions are considered in the team

Table 4.7 Your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
strongly agree	15	22.1	22.1	22.1
Agree	42	61.8	61.8	83.8
Neutral	3	4.4	4.4	88.2
Disagree	6	8.8	8.8	97.1
Strongly Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.7, the majority of the respondents 42 (61.8) agreed that Your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success, 15(22.1) strongly agreed it, 5(7.4) neutral 3(4.4) were disagreed it, 6(8.8%) and 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

Your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success

Figure 4.7 Your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success

Table 4.8 this organization always gives you freedom to do your work and listen your idea

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	29	42.6	42.6	42.6
Agree	24	35.3	35.3	77.9
Neutral	9	13.2	13.2	91.2
Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	95.6
Strongly Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.8, the majority of the respondents 29(42.6) were Strongly agreed that This organization always gives you freedom to do your work and listen your idea, 24(35.3) agreed it, 9(13.2) were neutral, 3(4.4) disagreed it and 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.8 his organization always gives you freedom to do your work and listen your idea

Table 4.9 Is the organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance’s future

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	21	30.9	30.9	30.9
Agree	26	38.2	38.2	69.1
Neutral	12	17.6	17.6	86.8
Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	91.2
Strongly Disagree	6	8.8	8.8	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.9, the majority of the respondents 26(38.2) agreed that It This organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance’s future, 21(30.9) strongly agreed it, 12(17.6) were neutral, 6(8.8) disagreed it, and 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it.

Is the organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance’s future

Figure 4.9 Is the organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance’s future

Table 4.10 The organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	18	26.5	26.5	26.5
Agree	36	52.9	52.9	79.4
Neutral	6	8.8	8.8	88.2
Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	92.6
Strongly Disagree	5	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.10, the majority of the respondents 36(52.9) strongly agreed that The organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team, 18(26.5) agreed it,6(8.8) were neutral, 5(7.4) strongly disagreed it, and 3(4.4) disagreed it.

The organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team

Figure 4.10 The organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team

Table 4.11 The organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	19	27.9	27.9	27.9
Agree	23	33.8	33.8	61.8
Neutral	17	25.0	25.0	86.8
Disagree	6	8.8	8.8	95.6
Strongly Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.11, the majority of the respondents 23(33.8) agreed that the organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly, 19(27.9) strongly agreed it, 17(25.0) were neutral, 6(8.8) dis agreed it, and 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it.

The organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly

Figure 4.11 The organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly

Table 4.12 The organization has not established an open line communication for ideas.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	15	22.1	22.1	22.1
Agree	24	35.3	35.3	57.4
Neutral	17	25.0	25.0	82.4
Disagree	4	5.9	5.9	88.2
Strongly Disagree	8	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.12, the majority of the respondents 24(35.3) agreed that The organization has not established an open line communication that makes you feel comfortable to approach him with ideas, 17(25.0) were neutral, 15(22.1) strongly agreed it, 8(11.8) strongly disagreed it, and 4(5.9) disagreed it.

The organization has not established an open line communication for ideas.

Figure 4.12 The organization has not established an open line communication for ideas.

Table 4.13The organization gives complete freedom competition for Decision making

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	16	23.5	23.5	23.5
Agree	26	38.2	38.2	61.8
Neutral	16	23.5	23.5	85.3
Disagree	6	8.8	8.8	94.1
Strongly Disagree	4	5.9	5.9	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.13, the majority of the respondents 26(38.2) agreed that The organization doesn't recognize the extra effort you put at work, 16(23.5) were neutral,16(23.5) strongly agreed it, 6(8.8) disagreed it, 4(5.9) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.13 The organization gives complete freedom competition for Decision making.

Table 4.14 The organization gives you complete freedom to do decisions, because they avoid making decisions

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	27	39.7	39.7	39.7
Agree	27	39.7	39.7	79.4
Neutral	8	11.8	11.8	91.2
Disagree	4	5.9	5.9	97.1
Strongly Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.14, the majority of the respondents 27(39.7) agreed that the organization gives you complete freedom to do decisions, because they avoid making decisions, 27(39.7) strongly agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 4(5.9) disagreed it, 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.14 The organization gives you complete freedom to do decisions, because they avoid making decisions

Table 4.15 the organization doesn't intervene in the work affairs of the subordinates

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly Agree	14	20.6	20.6	20.6
	Agree	20	29.4	29.4	50.0
	Neutral	15	22.1	22.1	72.1
	Disagree	13	19.1	19.1	91.2
	Strongly Disagree	6	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.15, the majority of the respondents 20(29.6) agreed that the organization doesn't want to intervene in the work affairs of the subordinates 15(22.1) were neutral, 14(20.6) strongly agreed it, 13(19.1) disagreed it, and 6(8.8) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.15 he organization doesn't intervene in the work affairs of the subordinates

Table 4.16 The directors always look the outcome of the work.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	41	60.3	60.3	60.3
Agree	10	14.7	14.7	75.0
Neutral	4	5.9	5.9	80.9
Disagree	5	7.4	7.4	88.2
Strongly Disagree	8	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.16, the majority of the respondents 41(60.3) strongly agreed that the directors always look the outcome of the work they are not considering the way you are doing the work, 10(14.7) agreed it, 8(11.8) strongly disagreed it, 5(7.4) disagreed it, 4(5.9) were neutral.

Figure 4.16 the directors always look the outcome of the work.

Table 4.17 Does The top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	20	29.4	29.4	29.4
Agree	33	48.5	48.5	77.9
Neutral	12	17.6	17.6	95.6
Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	98.5
Strongly Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.17, the majority of the respondents 33(48.5) agreed that the top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff, 20(29.4) strongly agreed it, 12(17.6%) were neutral, 2(2.9) disagreed, and 1(1.5) strongly disagreed it.

Does The top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff

Figure 4.17 Does the top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff

Table 4.18 does The projects that you undertake are always completed in time

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	21	30.9	30.9	30.9
Agree	24	35.3	35.3	66.2
Neutral	17	25.0	25.0	91.2
Disagree	5	7.4	7.4	98.5
Strongly Disagree	1	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.18, the majority of the respondents 24(35.3) agreed that the projects that you undertake are always completed in time, 21(30.9) strongly agreed it, 17(25.0) were neutral, 5(7.4) disagreed it, 1(1.5) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.18 does the projects that you undertake are always completed in time

Table 4.19 You always estimate the project completion times in your organization

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	28	41.2	41.2	41.2
Agree	27	39.7	39.7	80.9
Neutral	8	11.8	11.8	92.6
Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	95.6
Strongly Disagree	3	4.4	4.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.19, the majority of the respondents 28(41.2) strongly agreed that You always estimate the project completion times in your organization, 27(39.7) agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it, and 2(2.9) disagreed it.

Figure 4.19 you always estimate the project completion times in your organization

Table 4.20 you always value the hours of work required to complete a project

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Agree	29	42.6	42.6	42.6
Agree	24	35.3	35.3	77.9
Neutral	8	11.8	11.8	89.7
Disagree	2	2.9	2.9	92.6
Strongly Disagree	5	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	68	100.0	100.0	

According to Table 4.20, the majority of the respondents 29(42.6) strongly agreed that You always value the hours of work required to complete a project, 24(35.3) agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 5(7.4) disagreed it, while only 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

Figure 4.20 you always value the hours of work required to complete a project

CHAPTER FIVE

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4.0 INTRODUCTION

The data has been analyzed by using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20 as data analyzing tool. This chapter presents the results of the analysis in summary form and concludes the study process as a whole. Conclusion was based on specific objectives. The shape of the questionnaire in the demographic section is looked upon in terms of Gender, Age, Marital status, level of education and Experience

5.1 FINDINGS

The majority of the respondents 48(70.6%) were male, while only 20(29.4%) were female. This indicates that most of those who participated the study were male.

The majority of the respondents 23(33.8%) were between 28 – 37 years, 18(26.5%) were between 18 – 27 years, 11(16.2%) were between either 28 – 47 years or 48 – 57 years, while only 5(7.4%) were 58 and above years.

The majority of the respondents 43(63.2%) were married, while 25(36.8%) were single. This indicates that more married respondents participated the study than single participants.

The majority of the respondents 28(41.2%) were bachelor degree, 22(32.4%) were master level, 9(13.2%) were diploma level, 4(5.9%) were secondary level, while 5(7.4%) had other levels of education.

The majority of the respondents 62(91.2%) were employed, while 6(8.8%) were unemployed.

The majority of the respondents 29(42.6%) strongly agreed that You feel that your opinions are considered in the team, 25(36.8%) agreed it, 8(11.8%) were neutral, 4(5.9%) disagreed it, while only 2(2.9%) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 43(63.2) agreed that your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success, 15(22.1) strongly agreed it, 5(7.4) disagreed it, 3(4.4) were neutral and 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 29(42.6) were agreed that this organizational way gives you freedom to do your work and listen your idea, 25(36.8) agreed it, 9(13.2) were neutral, 2(2.9) disagreed it and 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 26(38.2) strongly agreed that It this organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance's future, 21(30.9) agreed it, 12(17.6) were neutral, 6(8.8) strongly disagreed it, and 3(4.4) disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 36(52.9) strongly agreed that the organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team, 18(26.5) agreed it, 6(8.8) were neutral, 5(7.4) strongly disagreed it, and 3(4.4) disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 24(35.3) agreed that the organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly, 19(27.9) strongly agreed it, 16(23.5) were neutral, 6(8.8) is agreed it, and 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 24(35.3) agreed that the organization has not established an open line communication that makes you feel comfortable to approach him with ideas, 17(25.0) were neutral, 15(22.1) strongly agreed it, 8(11.8) strongly disagreed it, and 4(5.9) disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 26(38.2) agreed that the organization doesn't recognize the extra effort you put at work, 16(23.5) were neutral, 16(23.5) strongly agreed it, 6(8.8) disagreed it, 4(5.9) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 27(39.7) agreed that the organization gives you complete freedom to do decisions, because they avoid making decisions, 27(39.7) strongly agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 4(5.9) disagreed it, 2(2.9) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 20(20.6) agreed that the organization doesn't want to intervene in the work affairs of the subordinates 15(22.1) were neutral, 14(20.6) strongly agreed it, 13(19.1) disagreed it, and 6(8.8) strongly disagreed it.

the majority of the respondents 41(60.3) strongly agreed that The directors always look the outcome of the work they are not considering the way you are doing the work, 10(14.7) agreed it, 8(11.8) strongly disagreed it, 5(7.4) disagreed it, 4(5.9) were neutral.

The majority of the respondents 33(48.5) agreed that the top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff, 20(29.4) strongly agreed it, 12(17.6%) were neutral, 2(2.9) disagreed, and 1(1.5) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 24(35.3) agreed that the projects that you undertake are always completed in time, 21(30.9) strongly agreed it, 17(25.0) were neutral, 5(7.4) disagreed it, 1(1.5) strongly disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 28(41.2) strongly agreed that you always estimate the project completion times in your organization, 27(39.7) agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 3(4.4) strongly disagreed it, and 2(2.9) disagreed it.

The majority of the respondents 29(42.6) strongly agreed that you always value the hours of work required to complete a project, 24(35.3) agreed it, 8(11.8) were neutral, 5(7.4) strongly disagreed it, while only 2(2.9) disagreed it.

5.2 CONCLUSION

Successfully managing a project from start to finish requires certain key skills. Scheduling, time management, and the ability to negotiate with internal and external parties are all critical competencies. Leadership, risk management, and critical thinking similarly all fall high on the list.

But the skill that is perhaps most important to project management is the one that underlies all of these others: Communication.

Without strong communication skills, project managers would find it incredibly difficult, if not impossible, to effectively manage their teams and coordinate efforts in order to bring about a project's successful resolution.

The researcher intended to collect primary data using questionnaire as a research instrument. Descriptive and cross sectional designs were used. This study targeted a population 82 and selected 68 respondents as sample. The shape of the questionnaire in the demographic section is looked upon in terms of Gender, Age, marital status, and level of education.

Analysis of data in this study was done concurrently with data collection. After data collection the questionnaires of respondents were sorted out accordingly; responses were verified, coded, categorized and entered into the computer using statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 software and excel program.

Most of respondents of this study 30(41.1%) were between 18-27 years and 28-47 years, while 4(5.9%) were 48-57 years and 58 and above. The researcher indicates the most of respondents were 18-27 years and 28-47 years old. Most of respondents of this study 50 (73.5 %) were single and 18(26.5%) were married. The researcher indicates the most of respondents were single. So the most of respondents were singles. Most of respondents of this study 20(29.4%) were Primary, secondary and Tertiary level, while only 8(11.8%) had no formal education level, so this result indicates that the most of respondents were Primary, secondary and Tertiary level. So the most of respondents are Primary, secondary and Tertiary. Most of respondents of this study 34(50%) were employed, and 34(50%) were unemployed. So the researcher indicates that the most of respondents were employed and unemployed. 38 respondents with the percentage of (55.9%) agreed that you feel that your opinions are considered in the team, 12 respondents with the percentage of (17.6%) strongly agreed it, 7 respondents with the percentage of (10.3%) were neutral. On the other hand, 7 other respondents with the percentage of (10.3%) strongly disagreed it, while only 4 respondents with the percentage of (5.9%) disagreed it.

5.2 Recommendation

In this section the researcher suggested some recommendations:

1. Although the study was carried out in Mogadishu, there is a need for further research across the whole country.
2. Other researchers should examine the ties between the study results and the reality that exists in the study area.
3. Other researchers are encouraged to test the generalizability of this study by conducting the same study in other districts within Mogadishu or other regions of Somalia.

APPENDIX QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender (Please Tick)

_____ (1) Male _____ (2) Female

Age (Please Tick)

Below 20	
20 - 29	
30 - 39	
40 - 49	
50 Above	

Qualifications Under Education Discipline (Please Tick):

Certificate	
Diploma	
Bachelors	
Masters	
Ph. D	
Others (Specify)	

Working Experience

1-2 years	
3-5 years	
6- above	

SECTION B: questionnaire to determine the level of communication

Direction: please tick your rating on the space under each column which corresponds to your best choice.

Rate	Response mode	Description	Interpretation
1	Strongly agree	You agree with no doubt at all	Very satisfactory
2	Agree	You agree with some doubt	Satisfactory
3	Disagree	You disagree with some doubt	Fair
4	Strongly disagree	You disagree with no doubt	Poor

Extent of communication		Rating			
No					
	Values and norms				
1	You feel that your opinions are considered in the team				
2	Your organization accepts input from the other members on matter that concerns the project success				
3	This organization always gives you freedom to do your work and listen your idea				
4	Is the organization has regular team meetings to discuss the current situation of the microfinance and to generate ideas of the microfinance's future				

	Organization management				
1	The organization makes major decisions without consulting with the entire team				
2	The organization closely monitors your work to ensure that you are performing correctly				
3	The organization has not established an open line communication for ideas				
4	The organization doesn't recognize the extra effort you put at work				

	Organization structure				
1	The organization gives you complete freedom to do decisions, because they avoid making decisions				
2	The organization doesn't want to intervene in the work affairs of the subordinates				
3	The directors always look the outcome of the work				
4	Does the top management in the organization has good relationship with lower staff				

SECTION B: questionnaire to determine the level of project performance

Direction: please tick your rating on the space under each column which corresponds to your best choice.

Rate	Response mode	Description	Interpretation
4	Strongly agree	You agree with no doubt at all	Very satisfactory
3	Agree	You agree with some doubt	Satisfactory
2	Disagree	You disagree with some doubt	Fair
1	Strongly disagree	You disagree with no doubt	Poor

Level of project performance		Rating			
No	Time of completion				
1	Does the projects that you undertake are always completed in time				
2	You always estimate the project completion times in your organization				
3	You always value the hours of work required to complete a project				
	Quality of project completed				
1	You ensure quality output for the projects that you undertake				
2	You generally feel that the projects that you undertake are successful				
3	The project activities that you undertake always make profit for the company				
4	You ensure quality working relationship between the project team and the client				
5	The projects that you undertake are completed in accordance with the original set standards				
	Scope/design				
1	You always make decisions with reference to the project scope				
2	your projects always need to be accomplished in order to deliver a service				
3	Your project features always meet the stake holders requirements				

4	Your project scope is always more work oriented				
5	Your project requirements are always well defined and described.				
	Budget				
1	The projects that you undertake are completed within budget				
2	The project budget that you undertake is always accepted by the users and clients				
3	You always find it easy to know how much it will cost before starting a project				
4	You always create an accurate budget				
5	Your project budget always includes a section for recording income sources and expenditure				

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